

CORRECTION

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Correction: Editorial Perspectives: 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2): what is its fate in urban water cycle and how can the water research community respond?

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Correction for 'Editorial Perspectives: 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2): what is its fate in urban water cycle and how can the water research community respond?' by Vincenzo Naddeo *et al.*, *Environ. Sci.: Water Res. Technol.*, 2020, 6, 1213–1216. DOI: 10.1039/D0EW90015J.

Following publication of this Editorial Perspective, it was brought to our attention that related work published online on 11th February 2020 existed. This related website should be credited.

In the section titled 'How can coronavirus occurrence in wastewater be minimized?' an additional reference should be included:

Water Environment Federation, The Water Professional's Guide to COVID-19, <https://www.wef.org/news-hub/wef-news/the-water-professionals-guide-to-the-2019-novel-coronavirus/> (accessed March 2020).

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

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